

Textbook: Focus on Students' National Identity

Projecting a modern textbook as personality developing educational environment

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Abstract

Due to changing pedagogical points of view about the aim and the content of education points of view about the target and functions of a modern textbook as a means of teaching are being transformed as well. For overall personality development students need textbooks which don't only transfer educational information of some volume and complexity but also represent full-sided conditions of a personality's interaction with a textbook as educational environment which is defined as a situation by the authors. According to the prevailing kind of students' orientation 4 qualitatively different types of such situations are defined: cognitive orientation, object and activity orientation, axiological orientation, integral orientation. Each of these types is placed in correspondence with 3 groups of personality developing environmental conditions (content sources, stimuli and opportunities for personality growth). This situational and environmental model given is placed on the basis of projecting a modern textbook and defines the criteria of evaluating its personality developing potential.

Keywords: personality developing educational environment, criteria of quality.

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Introduction

Today the traditional textbook has stopped being the only one source of educational information. There is even an opinion that "the textbook has died" (Kostyuk, 2021). Thanks to digitalization the list of sources of educational information has been considerably enriched for the last 30 years. Plenty of educational Internet resources and electronic educational courses have appeared. Specific computer programs for creating

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teachers' unique textbooks have been made. The diapason of functions of textbooks has been broadened as well. Besides giving fundamental information different models of textbooks are oriented to perform the following functions: to form applied knowledge (Nikolenko, 2020); to intensify the educational process (Pronin, 2020); to give the substantial basis for intercultural communication and dialogue (Pobedash, 2020); to use them as a means of education (Guz, 2020); as an instrument for creating students' individual educational trajectories (Dzenis, 2020). However, the issue of making an overall conception of a modern textbook, quality of which can be connected with achieving the most important aim in education – student's personality development, - remains opened in the pedagogical science so far.

The analysis of the foreign practice of education witnesses about the prevailing orientation of means of education towards pragmatic aims of education – forming rational knowledge and applied skills (YI, LI et al, 2018; Ummatqul Qizi, 2020) and towards national schools' achieving high results in testing quality of these knowledge and skills (Lewis, Sellar, Lingard, 2016).

The national pedagogical tradition in the Russian education doesn't restrict its aim only in training intelligent undergraduates that have a repertoire of theoretical knowledge and applied skills. In spite of the diversity of educational projects, implemented in Russian schools, colleges and universities, all of them find their place in the axiological field of the personality-oriented paradigm (Serikov, 2018 et al), which orients pedagogical workers to the value and target-based dominance of a student's personality development. It is not casual that education is defined as a united task-oriented process of teaching and training, which is realized not only on behalf of family, state and society but also person itself according to the federal law "About Education in the Russian Federation". In the interpretation of the law education implicates creating conditions for personality development as well as its capabilities, meeting its educational needs and interests, its self-determination. The idea of creating conditions for personality development is prior and core in making national educational standards and content of competencies reflected in them, in defining a social mission of any educational institute, in making programs of teaching and training.

We can't keep from remarking that in conditions of distant lessons conditions of education, which are popularly named educational environment, are being considerably transformed. If to look at the educational process among a pedagogical worker, students and environment, the functions of its organizing (planning, accounting, control, evaluating) are being allocated in a new way. Also means of presenting, perceiving, describing and understanding educational information are being changed. Forms of interaction between teachers and students as well as among students themselves are becoming principally different. Efficiency of a personality's education to much extent depends on completeness of functions of educational environment. Educational environment should be projected, on the one hand, as an integral pedagogical factor, positively influencing a student's personality. On the other hand, it should give opportunities for

showing personal activity of a student himself and a teacher as well. Interacting with educational environment, a student can be in principally different personality situations due to the extent of his subjective activity. These circumstances have caused the authors' attempt to create a model of a modern digital textbook, which can entirely take environmental factors and situational mechanisms of personality development in education into account.

Purpose and tasks of the study

The purposes of the research given are: a) to create model requirements to a modern textbook as personality developing educational environment, providing individual educational trajectories of consistent changing situations of a student's personality development on the basis of the situational and environmental approach; b) to verify the theoretic results taken during the analysis of advantages and restrictions of some textbooks on the English language, used by Russian teachers.

Literature review

A lot of projectors of educational systems (didactic systems of acquiring different competencies, training systems of forming certain personal traits, macrosystems of education of different levels, etc.) refer in their activity to famous conceptions of the environmental approach by Y.S. Manuylov, Y.P. Belozertsev, V.A. Yasvin, in which the educational process is projected as a complex of certain groups of conditions.

According to Y.S. Manuylov, environmental conditions of an educational process determine forming a personality with programmed traits (Manuylov, 2002). The structure of educational environment is represented with the two groups of conditions – static niches and dynamically changing natures. Niches in the environment are created by teachers and give various development opportunities to a student. Natures are defined as pedagogically uncontrolled (synergetic) factors, positively or negatively influencing a process of personality development (relations inside youngsters' communities, Internet impact, etc.). Pedagogical environment-forming activity comes to providing conditions-niches with targeted pedagogical meanings, strengthening impact of positive factors and weakening impact of negative factors. The proportion between niches and natures, got in the end, forms one or another kind of educational environment, producing one or another kind of personality.

Y.P. Belozertsev's conception of cultural and educational environment reveals the developing educational potential of natural, social and economic, cultural and historical conditions, in which a person's education is realized (Belozertsev, Baryshnikov, 2010). The main idea of this conception is in the specifically organized interaction between regional environment and education in which environmental conditions influence a student's personality evolvement and development (in this case students are objects of environmental impact), and participants of education, in their turn, influence the environment (taking a role

of subjects of influencing the environment). In the investigator's opinion, cultural and educational environment consists of three subsystems: 1) subject area of a personality's life activity, represented by ecological and geographical conditions, architectural peculiarities and infrastructure of the territory; this area does not have a task-oriented character of influencing a personality; 2) area of social and economic interrelations of individuals and groups, and also their interactions in terms of different subcultures, which also has extra pedagogical character; 3) area of institutional socialization, represented by religious and educational institutions and family, whose pedagogical impact on a personality is changeable and depends on prevailing mental and moral values.

In terms of V.A. Yasvin's research (Yasvin, 2020) educational environment is regarded as organized surround of a student, restricted by some area or events. This surround becomes personality developing environment if it is the subject of a student's personality energy, his activity and communication. Conditions, circumstances, events, factors, impacts and opportunities are related by the author to the structure of educational environment of personality development. Herewith, opportunities are described as areal and subjective, social and technological components of the environment. Pedagogical projection of educational environment of personality development is implemented via the point of interaction among elements of environment and a personality. And evaluation of personality developing potential of environment is implemented on the basis of vector modelling – graphic interpretation of environmental parameters in terms of a 2D coordinate system. Environmental parameters “activity-inactivity” are the vertical oriented line, and parameters “freedom-dependence” are the horizontal oriented line.

During the last decades a focus area, connected with investigating conditions of personality development in education, and elaborating technologies of their creation, has been actively developing. These conditions are modelled by scientists with the help of terms “educational situation of personality development” (Serikov, 2012) and “personality developing educational environment” (Khodyakova, 2013). The representatives of the school of thought of personality-oriented education have shown that the main result of education should be students' acquiring personality experience – experience of performing the specific personality functions on their life way: motivation, goal-setting, sense searching, value system, selectiveness, responsibility, dialogueness, empathy, volitional self-regulation, creativity, etc. And knowledge, skills and competencies will be naturally formed in the process of collecting personality experience as its subjectified and concretized content. It is proved that personality experience cannot be transferred directly from a teacher to a student. A teacher can just create conditions, in which these functions will be highly requested (actualized). Thus, for example, senses of educational activity aren't in this activity itself. Wider cultural and environmental context is needed for their appearing. Perceiving this context, a personality forms its own sense attitude (Leontyev, 2012). A capability to keep an interpersonal dialogue is formed in a student's mind only in specific situations of hermeneutical communication (Samoylov, 2001). A situation of personality development is regarded as a unit of projecting personality-

oriented educational systems (Bondarenko, Artyukhina, 2014, et al). In terms of the discussed school of thought pedagogical technologies of making application and task-oriented situations (Danilchuk, 1997), discussive and dialogical situations (Belova, 2006) are created.

The situational and environmental methodological approach (Khodyakova, 2013) allows to overcome the restriction of the environmental approach in the part of uncontrolled influence of chaotic environmental factors. However, this approach has not been used in projecting a modern textbook so far.

Methodology

According to the situational and environmental approach the educational process is projected by a pedagogical worker via environmental conditions which perform the functions of content sources (CS), stimuli (S) and opportunities (O) for personality development. The unit of projecting an educational process is a personality developing situation which is such an interaction among environmental and personality factors of personality growth, that leads to collecting personality (reflective and creative) experience. There are four kinds of situations of personality development that differ qualitatively:

1) a situation of cognitive orientation (SCO) in educational environment. Being in the situation of such a kind, a student adapts to educational environment, which is new for him. He studies its rules and requirements, forms a system of basic knowledge in the sphere of studying, acquires experience in activity according to an example or an instruction. He also acquires experience in representing knowledge and defined methods of activity. Pedagogical projection of educational environment is realized in placing certain demands on a student, in positive encouraging him in his educational progress (environmental conditions – stimuli), in providing him with systematized educational information and rules of performing educational activity (environmental content conditions), and also in finding the educational regime, appropriate for every student, and supporting him with the necessary instrumental means of learning (environmental conditions – opportunities);

2) a situation of object and activity orientation in educational environment (SOAO). In this situation a student structurizes educational environment in accordance with his own educational needs and subjective interests. He is ready to manage his studying independently: to look for information, to define an order of performed actions, to choose fluently a level of complexity of educational tasks and means of doing them. In this situation he perceives his individual capabilities and opportunities, he compares his educational results with results of others. He gets experience of selective activity, motivation and goal-setting. Pedagogical projection of educational environment is realized in giving a student alternative sources of educational information (environmental content conditions), in creating conditions for gaming and competitive activity (environmental conditions – stimuli) and in providing him with various forms, methods and means of educational activity (environmental conditions – opportunities);

3) a situation of axiological orientation (SAO) in educational environment. Being in a situation of such a kind, a student has already got perception about educational environment, his own interests and opportunities. At this time, he feels necessity to search for personality senses of his learning and to define his personality position towards one or another subjective sphere, because without it pointing his own life perspectives and making plans about his further education is impossible. In the situation of such a kind experience of reflective activity and dialogical communication is acquired. Pedagogical projection of educational environment is realized in showing integral images of outstanding personalities in this sphere of knowledge or meaningful events taken from history of the corresponding science (environmental content conditions) to a student, in providing conditions for axiological dialogue with students (environmental conditions – opportunities), in including a problematic context into an educational process or contradictions and collisions, which need to be resolved, and also in external social evaluating students' sayings (environmental conditions – stimuli).

4) a situation of integral orientation (SIO) in educational environment. This situation is characterized by a student's personality position (namely a system of axiological attitudes towards educational environment and towards himself in this environment), which he is ready to check practically during studying and communication. In the situation of such a kind experience of creative thinking and self-realization is acquired. In this situation a teacher – projector of educational environment – should give the maximal extent of freedom in transforming and supplementing informational content of education (environmental content conditions) to a student, in multimedia illustrating materials studied, as well as in collaborating with other participants of an educational process (environmental conditions – opportunities) and in public stating a personality position in creative competitions, at scientific conferences, etc. (environmental conditions – stimuli).

Results

A variant of an electronic textbook, which has already become traditional, is suitable for the first kind of a situation of personality development. An introduction in such a textbook defines aims of studying and requirements to a student. The main body has educational materials which should be learned and which are structured as hypertext. A module of programmed studying is used as an appendix. It has an automatic knowledge controller and instrumental environment for doing exercises of using knowledge with all the necessary instructions and examples-samples. Every successful action of a student in this module is followed by a corresponding screen message.

A textbook-“constructor” with a possibility to create an individual educational trajectory of independent learning out of a complex of content blocks and a list of various instruments, represented in it, fits the second kind of a situation of personality development. Content blocks allow to consider the same educational topic in different aspects, from different scientific points of view, etc. Besides offering the

choice of forms, methods and means of studying, instrumental blocks include gaming modules, which are made for one, two students and more, and provide objective evaluations on the basis of gage criteria.

The third kind of a situation of personality development is oriented to a wide social and cultural foil of education and requires performing functions of “a cultural navigator and a partner in communication” from a textbook. The function of a navigator in the textbook can be performed by hyperlinks to electronic informational resources on the Internet, which fit a topic studied, as well as specific problem-targeted blocks for each of the topics studied. The function of a partner in communication can be performed with the help of including into a textbook a chresthomatic block of fragments from works of literature or art, memorial and biographic, historical sources as well as blocks of questions “for finding significance”, which can be answered by a student in a form of written or audio essays in a specific appendix to the textbook.

In the situation of the fourth kind a textbook-“laboratory” is needed, a book, where students’ creative experiments are possible, where they can actualize their individual ideas and projects, made in collaboration with other students, on one or another subject. A student should have the opportunity to attach informational blocks, created by himself, multimedia presentations and video materials, references to personal accounts, comprising results of his learning, as well as portfolio of achievements, significant for him (scientific performances, participation in competitions on the topic of a subject studied, publications, etc.), to a textbook.

Discussions

The ideal model of a personality developing textbook given is hard to actualize in educational practice, the more so because opportunities of individual education are reduced in Russian education, and an educational process is usually programmed considering its mass character and a class-and-lesson structure of its organization. Nevertheless, in our opinion, conditions of educational environment of a textbook should meet every student’s development needs, because he can be in any of the four discussed situations. It means that a modern textbook should meet all mentioned personality developing requirements.

Using the example of textbooks on the English language, let’s see how students’ personality developing potential can be evaluated on the basis of these criterial requirements. We will point “+” to show accordance between characteristics of textbooks and the described criteria, and “-” to show their discordance. Summarizing personality developing scores will let us make a rating of the analyzed textbooks. The closer total score is to number 12, characterizing maximal completeness of its personality developing features, the more qualified a textbook is.

Table 1. The example of evaluating textbooks on the English language on the basis of personality developing criteria

“Quizlet” as an electronic assistant, an app	-	+	+	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	4
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Conclusion

To sum up the conducted research, we can make the following conclusions:

- a modern textbook should create conditions for actualizing the main aim of education – a student’s personality development, due to which it should be projected as educational environment, providing a student with conditions, necessary for his personality experience development, such as content sources, stimuli and processual opportunities;
- interacting with educational environment, a student is in a situation of one of the four kinds: cognitive orientation, object and activity orientation, axiological orientation and integral orientation. To make this situation personality developing and causing passing to a situation of the next kind, it should be provided with environmental conditions, correspondent to each kind of orientation; these conditions define criterial requirements to a textbook as personality developing educational environment;
- the analysis of the textbooks on the English language, actualized on the basis of criterial requirements, shows that a) their personality developing potential can be objectively evaluated on the basis of ranking them according to a sum of personality developing features; b) the most problematic zone in projecting modern textbooks is providing students’ axiological and integral orientation which requires correcting the existing approaches to creating textbooks.

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